

Interrogating *The Drowned World* through Timothy Morton's *Hyperobjectivity*

Dr. P S Subrahmanya Bhat,
Professor of English,
Karnatak Arts College Dharwad,
Karnataka, India.

Apoorva Chikmath,
PhD Reaserch Scholar,
Karnatak University Dharwad,
Karnataka, India.

Abstract: *Although J.G. Ballard's The Drowned World was published in 1962, decades before Anthropocentrism and Timothy Morton's Theory of Hyperobjectivity came into existence, it perfectly anticipates the challenges posed by climate change in the 21st century. The novel serves as a literary articulation of the theory postulated by Timothy Morton in his work Hyperobjects: Philosophy and Ecology after the End of the World. In Ballard's The Drowned World, climate change acts as a dominant force that shapes human perception, the ecosystem and non-human agencies. This article argues that the flooded world in The Drowned World complies with the properties of hyperobjects as defined by Timothy Morton- viscosity, nonlocality, temporal undulation, phasing and interobjectivity; demonstrating that Ballard's novel anticipates the challenges posed by climate change decades before they are named.*

Keywords: J.G. Ballard, The Drowned World, Hyperobjectivity, Climate Change, Timothy Morton

Climate change is often considered a distinctly contemporary problem, rooted in late 20th century scientific discourse and political urgency. However, certain literary works anticipated the consequences of climate change on the ecosystem and human perception. J.G. Ballard's *The Drowned World*, published in 1962, is one such example. Ballard has portrayed what a future climate change-ravaged world would look like and the consequences it would have on human and non-human

agencies by picturing a flooded earth, drowned cities, and the emergence of new and mutated species. The novel imagines the future Earth transformed by rising temperatures, melting ice caps and global flooding. Ballard's focus is not merely on catastrophe but also on the transformation of human perception, memory and desire under planetary conditions that exceed human comprehension.

Timothy Morton's concept of hyperobjects, as postulated in *Hyperobjects: Philosophy and Ecology after the End of the World*, offers a compelling framework for understanding why *The Drowned World* stands strikingly relevant in the age of climate crisis. Hyperobjects are entities that are massively distributed in time and space and are beyond human perception. Climate change is Morton's central example of such an entity. This article argues that *The Drowned World* fits precisely into Morton's theory of Hyperobjectivity.

The Drowned World has been interpreted through various critical lenses, most prominent among which are reading the novel through the lens of ecological and environmental themes, psychological perspective, gender dynamics, etc. Cenk Tan, in his PhD thesis titled "An Ecocritical Study of J G Ballard's Climate Fiction Novels, studies *The Drowned World* through an ecofeminist perspective. The author puts the character of Beatrice in the spotlight, highlighting how Beatrice is the only female character in the novel and draws similarities between the situation of Beatrice and the natural world in the novel. According to the author, both Beatrice and the natural world are subject to male domination and patriarchy. He writes how capitalism impacts the life of Beatrice and the natural world around. Cenk Tan says, "There exists a parallel condition between Beatrice, the only woman left in London and Earth. From an ecofeminist point of view, both have been discriminated, exploited and abused by the patriarchal, capitalist world order" (Tan,87). Jim Clarke, in his article "Reading Climate Change in Ballard", takes a climatological approach to interpret the novel. He notes how the

civilisation is dominated and defined by the environment and how the characters in the novel traverse through psychological states affected by it. The narrative of Ballard's climate dystopias is post-apocalyptic, meaning the disaster has already occurred and is not preventable (Clarke, 9). Clarke points out that Ballard's antipathy towards the scientific community and science as a whole is depicted in the novel. It can be seen through the existential pointlessness of the monitoring work conducted at the lagoon station (10). He writes, "Ballard depicts a world where, though climate change has already occurred and is accelerating, the scientific method is ironically still trapped in a superseded paradigm of hypothesising before reacting" (11). He is of the view that Ballard's novels are distant from contemporary climate fiction because the visions of climate change are diachronically displaced from the issues and debates that arose out of climatic global warming concerns, and they contain no discussion of blame or responsibility, and no attempt at mitigation (Clarke, 19). Ecopsychology is another interesting lens through which *The Drowned World* can be studied. In an article titled "The Psychological Landscape of Ecological Disaster in J.G. Ballard's Fiction", Miss Sheetal and Dr Narendra Kumar have explored Ecopsychology as an interdisciplinary field that explores the relationship between human psychology and the earth's environmental systems. The article discusses about the scope of Ecopsychology in examining how characters' interactions with their environments reflect broader psychological and ecological themes. The study highlights how the literature can portray the psychological impacts of environmental issues, offering insights into how individuals and societies perceive and react to ecological disorders. In another article titled "A Clock Less Urgent- Work, Leisure and Time in J.G. Ballard's *The Drowned World* and *Vermilion Sands*", the author Christopher Webb draws an interesting argument on the deliberate complication of time in Ballard's *The Drowned World* and its response to a certain shift in mid-twentieth century evaluations of work and leisure. Webb calls the characters in Ballard's novel displaced and disoriented late capitalist subjects whose experience of time is transformed by the

weird temporality of the landscapes in which they find themselves (1). He draws his argument based on the idea given by Simon Sellars that the recurring theme in Ballard's writing throughout the 1960s is the idea of escaping or cheating time, precipitated by a period of psychic turmoil (4). He argues that *The Drowned World* imagines a world that has slipped back into a pre-human past in which the very idea of leisure seems absurdly irrelevant and distinguishes two types of time concepts that compete with each other in this altered world. One is the clock time, the one that most of the characters use to control and sense a new environment, and the other is deep time, which is an inner psychological time that has begun to take over the characters in their growing isolation and steers them away from the human environment towards a radically new environment (14). He argues that the absence of standardised clock time leads directly to the dissolution of the human subject. While these perspectives provide a wide range of interpretations of the novel, Timothy Morton's concept of Hyperobjectivity offers a distinctly new critical lens for reading J. G. Ballard's *The Drowned World*, especially when compared to earlier psychoanalytic, modernist, or environmental-humanist interpretations. What Morton enables is a shift away from human-centered meaning toward an ontology in which climate itself becomes an active, overwhelming presence that exceeds narrative, psychology, and ethics.

Although written decades earlier, the novel anticipates the theoretical ideas discussed by Timothy Morton in his *Hyperobjectivity*. Timothy Morton, in his book "Hyperobjectivity: Philosophy and ecology after the End of the World", describes Hyperobjects as "things that are massively distributed in time and space" (Morton, 1). Hyperobjects may be directly manufactured by humans or may occur naturally. Hyperobjects have a crucial impact on human beings, and they are directly responsible for the end of the world (Morton, 2). Hyperobjects exceed conventional human understanding. They infiltrate bodies, environments, and psychological states. Hyperobjects are not some imaginary objects, but they exist in reality. They are real whether humans believe in

them or not. Reading climate as a hyperobject and not just as a setting in the novel provides a completely new perspective for studying Ballard's *The Drowned World*.

Reading Ballard through the lens of Morton's Hyperobjectivity enables a deeper understanding of the ecocritical property of the novel. Climate change and ecological disaster don't play a background role in Ballard. Rather, Ballard frames the entire narrative around Climate change and its uncontrollable force that drives throughout the novel. Environmental disaster manifests itself as a hyperobject in Ballard's novel. Morton argues that every time one tries to pull free from hyperobjects, the more hopelessly stuck one is to them (Morton, 29). This stickiness or entanglement is seen throughout Ballard's novel. The paper analyses the novel *Drowned World* through the properties of hyperobjects, including viscosity, Nonlocality, Temporal Undulation, Phasing, and Interobjectivity.

Timothy Morton, in his book "Hyperobjectivity: Philosophy and ecology after the End of the World", describes Hyperobjects as "things that are massively distributed in time and space" (Morton, 1). He coined the term hyperobjects in his work "The Ecological Thought". A hyperobject could be anything that is widely distributed or spread across in huge quantities. It could be the Lago Agrio oil field in Ecuador, or the Florida Everglades, or the biosphere, or the Solar System, or the total of all nuclear materials on the Earth or simply climate change, or global warming itself (Morton, 1). According to Morton, "Hyperobjects are not just collections, systems, or assemblages of other objects. They are objects in their own right" (2). Hyperobjects cannot be fully seen, touched, or comprehended. Humans perceive only localised manifestations or symptoms of Hyperobjects. Global warming, for example, cannot be observed in its totality; it appears through heat waves, storms, droughts, polar melting, and ocean level rise. Hyperobjects are not merely external phenomena; they infiltrate thought, bodies, and infrastructures. Morton identifies

several defining properties of Hyperobjects, namely Viscosity, Non Locality, Temporal Undulation, Phasing and Interobjectivity.

One of Morton's key claims is that Hyperobjects are viscous, meaning they are always stuck to us. One can't get away with them. This very closeness of hyperobjects is a menace. Morton is of the view that we are not the sole actors on a stage called "Earth." Rather, we are caught in a sticky, interdependent relationship with nonhuman entities that are far larger and more lasting than we are. Climate change, in this sense, is not an external problem to be solved but a condition that permeates everyday existence. In *The Drowned World*, climate change is profoundly viscous. "By noon, less than four hours away, the water would seem to burn" (Ballard, 7). The characters in the novel *The Drowned World* cannot escape from the effects of climate change. They are always entangled with them throughout the novel. This defines the characteristic of stickiness or viscosity in the novel. The climate clings to their skin, their minds, and their psychological states. The heat described in the novel illustrates viscosity literally. Early in the novel, Kerans experiences the climate as an unavoidable force:

"Temperature at the equator are up to one hundred and eighty degree now, going up steadily, and the rain belts are continuous as high as the 20th parallel. There's more slit too—" (Ballard, 15).

This mirrors Morton's notion that hyperobjects adhere to bodies. Global warming becomes intimate and tactile. Even standing still, the characters sweat, hallucinate, and grow fatigued. The climate crisis is not an external threat but something absorbed through pores and lungs.

As the environment shifts toward a Triassic ecology, characters undergo psychological regression. Beatrice feels "one or two strange and peculiar nightmares" (28). Morton argues that hyperobjects disrupt human identity by forcing us into relations we cannot escape. Ballard literalizes this; the climate gets inside the

subconscious. The dreams are not metaphors; they are viscosity made psychological. The terrestrial and psychic landscapes clung to the characters and appeared real. Ballard writes, “Just as the distinction between the latent and manifest contents of the dream had ceased to be valid, so had any division between the real and the surreal in the external world. Phantoms slid imperceptibly from nightmare to reality and back again, the terrestrial and psychic landscapes were now indistinguishable” (74).

Even attempts to leave the drowned world fail. When Riggs orders the evacuation north, many characters feel unable or unwilling to abandon the environment. Hyperobjects trap humans not through physical imprisonment but through entanglement with systems like geological, biological, psychological. Ballard shows climate as something one can neither escape nor confront directly. Humans merely inhabit symptoms of a much larger phenomenon.

Morton defines hyperobjects as nonlocal, meaning they cannot be fully experienced in any one place or moment. Non-Locality of hyperobjects signifies that the effects of hyperobjects are distributed globally. They transcend human boundaries. The hyperobject as a whole cannot be seen or felt from a single place. Morton takes the help of an example of the invisibility of nuclear radiation to explain non-locality. He says that though nuclear accidents occur thousands of miles away in places like Chernobyl and Fukushima, the unseen radioactive particles float in the air and years later, some humans die of radiation sickness (Morton, 38). This proves that Hyperobjects cannot be experienced in full; only scattered manifestations are perceptible. Ballard’s drowned London exemplifies this property. London is merely one node in a vast web of climate transformation. The military base receives reports of submerged European cities, shifting equatorial lines, and global migrations. These distant events appear only in fragments, reinforcing nonlocality. Morton signifies that hyperobjects inhabit a Humean causal system (a philosophy in which it is perceived that one event causes another, but only the constant conjunction of events is experienced) in which association, correlation and

probability are the only things that go on (Morton, 19). In chapter two, Ballard writes, “New sea completely altered the shape and contours of the continents. The Mediterranean contracted into a system of inland lakes, and the British Isles were linked again with northern France. The Caribbean Sea was transformed into a desert of silt and salt flats. Europe became a system of giant lagoons” (22). The characters never see these places. The reader only imagines them through partial reports. The altered world cannot be grasped in totality. London’s lagoon is not the hyperobject but a symptom of global warming. Morton insists that hyperobjects appear only through localised effects. Ballard’s lagoon functions as one such effect. The novel’s refusal to show the entire world dramatises nonlocality. The catastrophic reversion of the climate is planet-scaled, yet the narrative remains confined to a few square miles. The characters and by extension, the reader, must confront the limits of human perception. The setting is almost set in the submerged city of London, and the information about the other regions across the globe is portrayed through reports received in stations.

According to Morton, Hyperobjects exist within deep time, a scale so vast that it is beyond human experience. This is a temporal undulation of hyperobjects. Morton brings in the concept of the light cone from relativity to illustrate that beyond its boundaries, our distinctions between “now,” “here,” and “past” collapse. Events outside of that light cone cannot be assigned to any distinct point in time or space, so the future can seep into the present. This leads to what he calls downward causation, where hyperobjects influence shorter-lived entities like us. Hyperobjects operate across vast temporal scales, and Ballard’s novel foregrounds time as a destabilised, nonhuman phenomenon. In *The Drowned World*, the climate’s transformation is not merely futuristic; it is prehistoric. The world reverts to conditions resembling the Triassic or Palaeozoic eras: giant ferns, reptilian fauna, and tropical lagoons. Time collapses into a cyclical structure. Ballard writes, “Impenetrable Mato Grossos sometimes three hundred feet high, they were a nightmare world of competing

organic forms returning rapidly to their Paleozoic past” (19). Human attempts to maintain civilisation- military hierarchy, scientific routines, and scheduling appear trivial. Planetary time overwhelms human time. Riggs’s schedules feel absurd against the backdrop of Earth’s geological cycles. Ballard thus dramatises the insignificance of anthropocentric temporality.

Hyperobjects like climate change, global warming, or radioactive waste are so massively distributed in time and space that humans can’t experience them all at once. Instead, we encounter them only in fragments, moments, or phases, much like how you only see one slice of the moon at a time. This is the phasing of hyperobjects. According to Morton, “Hyperobjects are phased: they occupy a high-dimensional phase space that makes them impossible to see as a whole on a regular three-dimensional human scale basis. We can only see pieces of hyperobjects at a time (Morton, 70). In *The Drowned World*, the effects of climate change are not seen as a whole; instead, through various moments like burning sun, storms that erode the surface of water, and occasional appearances of mutated species and through the occasional dreams of the characters.

Hyperobjects do not exist independently but through relationships among countless entities. Hyperobjects like climate change, radioactive waste, or global warming are massively distributed in time and space. We can’t encounter them in their totality; instead, we detect them through other objects. For example, climate change becomes visible via rising sea levels, melting ice, or species migration. These clues exist in an interobjective space, a network of signals and effects linking many objects together. This property of interobjectivity of hyperobjects exists through relationships between radiation, atmosphere, organisms, water, sediment, and human bodies. Ballard’s novel is filled with networks. The novel’s ecosystem is not merely hotter; it is transformed. Tropical vegetation proliferates at extraordinary rates; reptiles mutate; microbial life booms. The environment’s biological response is intertwined with solar radiation and climate.

Morton calls this “the mesh”—a dense network of interdependent processes. Kerans and the others are not observers but participants in this mesh. Their bodies adapt- sleeplessness, disorientation, lethargy, dream states. The scientists’ instruments corrode, boats rot, buildings decompose. The hyperobject connects everything. Buildings become artificial reefs; lagoons reclaim streets. Interobjectivity reveals itself through the dissolution of boundaries.

Although written in 1962, *The Drowned World* fits precisely into Timothy Morton’s theory of Hyperobjectivity. Morton’s hyperobjectivity allows *The Drowned World* to be read not as a metaphor for human decline or ecological warning but as an early fictional articulation of Anthropocene, in which climate emerges as a dominant, nonhuman agent. This is what fundamentally distinguishes a hyperobject-oriented reading from other criticism, i.e. it does not interpret the drowned world, it inhabits it. Morton provides a transformative framework for reading J. G. Ballard’s *The Drowned World*, one that moves beyond symbolic, psychological, and humanist interpretations toward a posthuman understanding of climate and agency. Hyperobjectivity allows the drowned landscape to be understood as the manifestation of a massively distributed, nonhuman force that exceeds human perception, control, and narrative comprehension. By foregrounding the properties of hyperobjects like nonlocality, viscosity, temporal vastness, and phased appearance, Morton’s theory illuminates Ballard’s depiction of a world in which human subjectivity is increasingly destabilised. Hyperobjectivity reframes *The Drowned World* as a narrative of slow catastrophe rather than apocalyptic rupture. The absence of dramatic climactic events, heroic resistance, or restorative closure aligns with Morton’s claim that ecological crisis unfolds as an ongoing condition rather than a singular endpoint.

Though Morton theorized hyperobjects fifty years after Ballard, *The Drowned World* anticipates all five properties. The novel understands climate as a distributed, massive, entangled force that exceeds comprehension. Ballard does not present

ecological catastrophe as a human-centered narrative. Instead, he writes the planet as the protagonist. Hyperobjects produce the uncanny: familiar environments become strange. The drowned city is both recognisable and alien. Ballard's *The Drowned World* provides a remarkably prescient literary model for understanding hyperobjects. By presenting global warming not as a solvable problem but as a planetary force that infiltrates bodies, dreams, ecosystems, and consciousness, Ballard constructs a narrative about humanity's entanglement with nonhuman forces. The novel challenges anthropocentrism by revealing the limits of human agency and perception. Ballard refuses to offer solutions or redemption; instead, he exposes the terrifying beauty of a world where planetary processes exceed human control. In this sense, *The Drowned World* stands as an early ecological novel that anticipates contemporary theories of the Anthropocene and hyperobjects, making it a crucial text for understanding the philosophical implications of living within vast, interconnected, and incomprehensible systems.

Works Cited

- National Geographic Society. "Anthropocene." Education. [nationalgeographic.org](https://www.nationalgeographic.org/education/anthropocene/), National Geographic, 19 Oct. 2023, education.nationalgeographic.org/resource/anthropocene/.
- Haraway, Donna. *Staying with the Trouble: Making Kin in the Chthulucene*. Duke University Press, 2016.
- Ballard, J. G. *The Drowned World*. 1962. Fourth Estate, 2014. Accessed 26 July 2025.
- Morton, Timothy. *Hyperobjects: Philosophy and Ecology after the End of the World*. Minneapolis, University Of Minnesota Press, 2013.
- Tan, Cenk. *An Ecocritical Study of J.G. Ballard's Climate Fiction Novels*. Oct. 2009. Accessed 25 Sept. 2025.
- Sheetal, and Dr Narendra Kumar. "The Psychological Landscape of Ecological Disaster in J. G. Ballard's Fiction." *International Journal of English Language*,

- Literature and Translation Studies (IJELR)*, vol. 12, no. 1, 2025, <http://www.ijelr.in/>. Accessed 1 Dec. 2025.
- Clarke, Jim. "Reading Climate Change in J.G. Ballard." *Critical Survey*, vol. 25, no. 2, 2013, pp. 7–21. *JSTOR*, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/42751031>. Accessed 16 Dec. 2025.
- Webb, Christopher. "A 'CLOCK LESS URGENT' Work, Leisure and Time in J. G. Ballard's the Drowned World and Vermilion Sands." *PULSE: The Journal of Science and Culture*, vol. 7, 2020. Accessed 1 Dec. 2025.
- Tait, Adrain. "Nature Reclaims Her Own: J. G. Ballard's the Drowned World." *Australian Humanities Review*, vol. 57, 2014, pp. 25–41. Accessed 1 Dec. 2025.